

USE OF SPEECH-ORIENTED GAMES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: this article is about the importance of using speech-oriented games in foreign language lessons. It also recommends types of speech-oriented games and provides insights into their significance in language learning.

Key words: speech communication etiquette, dialogic speech, speech situation, educational games, mental stress, psychological impact.

INTRODUCTION

In foreign language teaching one of the main goals is to develop speech skills and competencies. Teaching methods for speaking, reading, listening and writing have been crucial issues in foreign language pedagogy. Many researchers and methodologists have explored the ways to develop speech competencies. As a result of their research, intensive and interactive methods for foreign language teaching were developed, exercises and didactic games were created, and research on teaching processes was conducted.

To motivate students to learn a foreign language, it is essential to organize the learning process in a way that leads to high motivation and activity. Psychologists have offered the following recommendations:

1. The learning process should not cause physical or mental stress.
2. It should instill confidence in the students.

3. It should help develop various psychological traits in students.
4. It should foster communication skills and initiative.
5. It should cultivate love for the native language, patriotism, humanism, and strong moral beliefs in students during the process of foreign language learning.

METHODOLOGY

Using games in foreign language lessons plays an essential role in increasing students' interest in the language. Games can be applied in each lesson in accordance with the educational goals and objectives. They enhance the effectiveness of lessons, help students quickly and easily assimilate material from textbooks, and improve their communicative skills. Games in foreign language lessons are effective; as they stimulate emotional and intellectual engagement, require decision-making, expressing opinions, and finding ways to achieve success. These activities accelerate cognitive functions and, in language learning situations, enable students to practice speaking in the foreign language. Through these games, students begin to learn a foreign language in a way that feels natural and engaging.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The main aim of speech-oriented games is to develop speaking skills and competencies. Additionally, these games help students use foreign language phrases in communicative situations. Games are beneficial in reducing psychological barriers, such as fear of making mistakes, and encourage students to express their thoughts freely. Another benefit of using games for teaching is that both high-achieving and low-achieving students can succeed in these activities, creating an equal environment that fosters joy and reduces shyness. This helps students feel satisfaction and makes learning more enjoyable. Moreover, using action-oriented games and exercises in the foreign language learning process also positively affects students' physical development.

Examples of Speech-Oriented Games in Foreign Language Lessons:

1. Project Game - Food Recipes: Students are divided into groups. Each group creates its own recipe and presents it. Special experts on healthy eating offer their opinions.
2. Role-Playing Game – "At the Supermarket": Students are divided into two groups, playing the roles of sellers and buyers. Role-playing games help students overcome psychological barriers such as the fear of making mistakes and encourage them to express their ideas freely.
3. "Translator Game": At least three participants are involved: one student plays the role of a foreigner, the second acts as a translator, and the third student plays the role of a local person. This game allows the use of various topics and speech situations, such as introductions, travel, sports, and professions. It helps develop dialogic speaking skills and encourages quick thinking and responsiveness in students.

CONCLUSION

It is important to emphasize that educational games performed in accordance with the speech situation not only develop students' logical thinking but also help their imaginations grow. Educational games aim to increase students' activity during the learning process. Furthermore, using games provides a more dynamic approach to assessing students' knowledge, differing from traditional methods. The primary criterion for evaluating students is their level of activity and their ability to express thoughts that align with the speech situation.

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